

BEYOND THE LAB-SCALE: PEROVSKITE PHOTOVOLTAIC FABRICATION AND INDUSTRIAL ASSESSMENT WITH AUTOMATED SLOT-DIE COATER

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ABSTRACT: During the last 15 years, perovskite (PVK) photovoltaics (PVs) attained immense progress in single junction devices and, nowadays, spearhead the development of commercially viable 2-T tandem devices. This achievement became possible due to the exceptional properties of this material class, permitting not only power conversion efficiencies beyond 26%, but also low-cost fabrication from solution by common printing techniques. A wide consensus of researchers and technologists is reached, considering perovskite semiconductors feasible for industrial-scale fabrication alongside the well-established silicon technology. While laboratory-scale work enabled fast material screening, characterization and process analysis, the transfer of the technology to industry is often not sufficiently treated. Most likely, in situ quality assessment is needed to ensure stable output for failure analysis early in the device fabrication. Here, we present a unique toolkit for simulating industrial conditions by employing a fully automated slot-die coater, sample handling, gas quenching as well as in situ characterization. We succeed in re-creating conditions of high-throughput industrial fabrication in a model box of about 10 m³ under ambient atmosphere. Using the model box, we can investigate the feasibility of large-scale perovskite fabrication in a very cost-effective manner, identifying possible failure modes and predicting fabrication yield in a close-to-realistic model environment.

Keywords: Narrow band-gap perovskite; perovskite upscaling; slot-die coating.

1 INTRODUCTION

Perovskite photovoltaics is the hot topic in PV community in the last years thanks to the high efficiency, low-cost production and wide engineering of the material compositions and configurations. [1-3] Upscaling is often a way to prove the possible industrialization of this material in PV context even though the equipment usually used are still at lab-scale level.

The upscaling from laboratory cells to module devices has extreme importance to exploit at market level the PVK PV technology. The PVK deposition is the most critical step process and several techniques (e.g. slot-die, blade coating, bar coating, spray coating etc) in combination with different quenching methods (e.g. antisolvent, gas-quenching, vacuum-quenching) are employed to get homogeneous layer and performance close to the one obtained on small area cell. [4]

The in-situ measurements are more rarely used to understand crystallization kinetics and nucleation of perovskites in the as-cast solution and the subsequent growth of nanocrystals. [5] The lack of proper probing techniques of the film formation process hinders the construction of a universal design principle that provides a rational guideline to improving the quality of perovskite films.

Here we want to provide a new chapter on perovskite towards industrialization. We used an automatic slot-die coater in a controlled non-inert environment to set up a gas-quenched perovskite deposition till 15x15 cm² substrate. We consistently change deposition parameters such as height of the slot-die, coating speed and air flow following the process evolution with in-situ reflectance imaging to probe the as-coated film and study crystallization kinetic and growth of PVK crystals in a industrial box environment. [6]

The machine apparatus made by RISE Technology S.R.L. is an automatic slot-die coater equipped with a robot arm

for sample handling, two hotplates, an UV-ozone lamp, a slot die head support and air knife.

The following routine is carried out (numbers in bracket are referred to the machine components involved):

1. Leveling of the slot die head on the sample to achieve a homogenous gap (1,2)
2. Retrieving the sample from the sample holder (0)
3. Uv-ozone treatment (6)
4. Coating of the perovskite ink (1,2)
5. Gas Quenching (3)
6. In situ characterization: Reflectance imaging
7. Modification of Parameters and repetition
8. Annealing (4,5)
9. Storing of Sample (0)
10. Parameters tuning and repetition

In this unique succession of events, we simulate industrial production and test all the steps, which are paramount to achieving high throughput and yield. We believe that, by identifying processes compatible with this setup, we can test all the necessary steps for commercialization of perovskites in a very resource efficient way. Due to the capability of cyclic processing and continuous repetition, we can model the consistency of yield and throughput, identifying possible challenges early on. For example, we found that it is very difficult to implement gas quenching in a way that is repetitive for every sample.

Figure 1: Automatic slot-die coater picture (a,b,c) and in-situ characterization scheme (d)

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We change deposition parameters such as height of the slot-die, coating speed and air flow according to the in-situ reflectance as simple optical facility. We can study the crystallization kinetics and the growth of PVK crystals in the designed “industrial box” in dry air (RH < 30%) environment.

Figure 2: Perovskite reflectance pathway (a) In situ reflectance apparatus (b) m-ONE facility provided by RISE technology (c) plot (V vs s) of direct and diffuse reflectance (d)

The high degree of automation of the machine allows a process loop to be created in which the deposition parameters are evaluated by diffuse and direct in-situ reflectometry. With this setup, diffuse and direct reflections are recorded at the front of the crystallisation during the quenching step. If the diffuse reflectance is greater than the direct reflectance, a false quenching process is taking place due to incorrect crystallisation driven by the breakdown between the nucleation and diffuse regimes of crystal growth. In both cases of imbalance of the crystallization pathways, we have recorded the diffuse and direct footprints of the film, and this fine control and process optimization steps are finally traced in the transition from a greyish perovskite film with high diffuse reflection to a semitransparent brown film with high specular reflection for 7.5x5 and 15x15 cm² substrates, respectively.

Moreover, we scale up to 15x15 cm² substrate the perovskite film with the optimized process routine carried out from parameters variation and correlation of reflectance.

Figure 3: Perovskite film and in situ direct reflectance plot (a,b,c)

3. CONCLUSION

Reflectance measurement can effectively provide information about the crystallization process. A direct high reflectance signal means high mirror-like PVK film. In the bad case, the amorphous phase is present because of solvent trapping, incorrect quenching and poor crystallinity. Tuning coating parameter and quenching time cause high quality perovskite film

This in situ methodology developed in conjunction with the industrial box can effectively provide a tool to understand and probe the gas quenching window for any PVK formulation adopted in principle for this type of process.

4. REFERENCES

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